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4 **Calcifying plankton: from biomineralization to global change**

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37 **Single-sentence summary of the review**

38
39 Better delineation of calcifying plankton traits is needed to accurately reflect biogeochemical
40 system dynamics.

41

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42 **Abstract**

43

44 The cycling of calcium carbonate (CaCO₃) in the ocean is closely linked to seawater
45 alkalinity and the regulation of atmospheric CO₂. In the modern pelagic ocean, almost all
46 CaCO₃ is produced by three groups of calcifying planktonic organisms: coccolithophores,
47 foraminifers, and shelled pteropods. We review the differences in functional traits that
48 define each group's unique role in the global carbon cycle and their sensitivity to climate
49 change and ocean acidification. This synthesis reveals that a single representation of
50 CaCO₃ in climate models is unlikely to accurately reflect system dynamics or their
51 impacts on biogeochemical cycling under climate change. We argue that understanding
52 past and future CaCO₃ cycle requires a better delineation of the traits that make up the
53 diversity of calcifying plankton groups.

54

55

56 Almost all CaCO₃ produced in the modern pelagic ocean is biologically mediated by three
57 major groups of calcifying plankton (Fig. 1): coccolithophores (single-celled haptophyte
58 algae), foraminifers (single-celled amoeboid protists), and shelled pteropods (pelagic
59 mollusks, hereafter referred to only as pteropods) (1, 2). Calcifying plankton contribute
60 to global carbon cycling via the dual formation of particulate organic carbon and CaCO₃,
61 which forms their hard exoskeletons. At the base of the food web (as primary producers
62 and primary consumers), these planktonic calcifying organisms have impacted carbon
63 dynamics since the Mesozoic (3). Key processes include regulation of surface water
64 alkalinity, ballasting of organic matter and alkalinity export, and establishment of a
65 pelagic carbonate buffer capable of influencing major CO₂ change (3-10).

66

67 Controls on the distribution and biomineralization of calcifying plankton, and how the
68 CaCO₃ they produce is cycled through the ocean, have major consequences for the carbon
69 cycle, air-sea CO₂ exchange and ecosystem functioning, yet none of the Earth System
70 Models included in the current Coupled Model Intercomparison Project (CMIP6)
71 explicitly represents these organisms (e.g., (11, 12)). The capacity of calcifying plankton
72 to produce CaCO₃ makes these organisms sensitive to ocean acidification (13-15),
73 reinforcing the need for a more comprehensive view of their physiological traits,
74 biogeography and ecology. We review these topics and their interactions with the carbon
75 cycle and climate across temporal scales (from cellular to geological), and the sensitivity
76 of each group to environmental change. While coccolithophores, foraminifera, and
77 pteropods, are individually well-studied, their roles in ocean biogeochemistry are rarely
78 examined together, especially since research has now identified how the particular group
79 traits are linked to higher order processes (e.g. (2, 16-21)). Here we offer a novel, cross-
80 scale comparison from biomineralization pathways to global CaCO₃ cycling revealing
81 emergent insights and key gaps that have been overlooked in group-specific studies.

82

83

84 **Biogeography and biocalcification in a changing ocean**

85

- 86 • *Patterns of diversity and biomass*

87

88 The three calcifying plankton groups vary in size, mass, trophic strategy, particulate
89 inorganic to organic carbon ratios (PIC:POC), and growth and calcification rates (Fig. 1,
90 Table S1). Nonetheless, the three groups exhibit similar latitudinal diversity patterns ((22-
91 25), additional references in Table S1), with highest diversity at low to mid latitudes and
92 lowest diversity at high latitudes (Fig. 2 A-C). This mirrors diversity patterns of other
93 groups across both marine and terrestrial ecosystems (26-31), indicating common
94 underlying factors such as temperature (32), niche diversity (33, 34) and resource
95 availability (35).

96
97 Although latitudinal biodiversity trends are similar, the three groups display differential
98 latitudinal patterns in standing stocks of biomass (here referring to organic plus inorganic
99 carbon) (Fig. 2 D-F) (e.g., (16, 24, 36, 37). Pteropods and foraminifers exhibit notably
100 higher relative biomass in the Southern Ocean (Fig. 2 E, F), while coccolithophores are
101 excluded in the polar regions (>65° S) (Fig. 2 D), possibly due to competitive exclusion
102 by diatoms (38). In the Northern Hemisphere coccolithophores are present in polar
103 regions (Fig 2D) including the Barents (39) and the Bering Sea shelves (40, 41).

104
105 The three groups also display distinct depth distributions (Fig. 2 G-H). Both
106 coccolithophores and foraminifers inhabit the surface to the pycnocline, with
107 coccolithophores confined to the photic zone and foraminifers occasionally dwelling
108 deeper (2, 17, 36, 37, 42, 43). Most pteropods can inhabit deeper waters and actively
109 migrate in the water column over daily and/or seasonal timescales (e.g., (44-48)). Mean
110 biomass differs for the three groups, with mean observed values of 0.7 +/- 0.65 mg C m⁻³
111 for pteropods, 0.88 +/- 0.48 mg C m⁻³ for coccolithophores and 0.02 +/- 0.06 mg C m⁻³
112 for foraminifers ((16, 22) Fig 2 D-F)). While mean biomass values of coccolithophores
113 and pteropods are similar, the upper ranges observed for pteropods are 4-5 times higher
114 than for coccolithophores (Fig 2 D and 2F, respectively), suggesting that although the
115 mechanisms driving calcifying plankton abundance may be similar, group-specific trait
116 differences lead to distinct roles in the carbon cycle.

117
118 These distribution patterns are influenced by environmental factors such as photic depth
119 (36), temperature (e.g., (19, 49-51), oxygen (52-55), nutrients (e.g., (56, 57)), carbonate
120 chemistry (14, 58, 59) and food availability (e.g., (20, 60-63). The pronounced differences
121 in environmental preferences among the three groups ultimately stem from their distinct
122 traits (Fig. 1, Table S1), providing the basis to disentangle relationships between
123 environmental factors, diversity and biomass distributions, and susceptibility to ocean
124 acidification.

125 126 ● ***Ocean acidification and biomineralization***

127
128 Biomineralization plays a crucial role in shaping the environmental preferences and
129 competitive abilities of calcifying plankton (Figs 1, 2; Table S1). While biomineralization
130 enables survival in diverse habitats (e.g. (21, 64)), it also makes calcifying plankton more
131 sensitive to ocean acidification than non-calcified organisms (13, 14, 65), potentially
132 leading to greater impacts on these groups than other plankton occupying similar niches.

133
134 In all three groups, CaCO₃ production takes place in a specialized biomineralization space
135 (Fig. 3), but the nature of the calcification site varies between groups, potentially
136 impacting their sensitivities to ocean acidification. In almost all coccolithophores, the
137 intracellular site of calcification (where individual CaCO₃ scales – called coccoliths - are

138 formed) is completely isolated from seawater by two membranes (66-68). The
139 extracellular calcification sites of foraminifers and pteropods are in principle open to
140 seawater, but in foraminifers this appears sealed from its surroundings (69). While the
141 calcification mechanism of pteropods is less well known, the calcification site of other
142 mollusks is typically closed, despite paracellular calcium transport from the haemolymph
143 (an extracellular fluid with functional similarities to blood and lymph of vertebrates) to
144 the site of calcification representing a limited opening to seawater (70-73).

145
146 In addition to seawater isolation degree, the source of inorganic carbon for calcification
147 also has important biogeochemical and fitness implications (74). For coccolithophores
148 and possibly foraminifers, the unique source of inorganic carbon is HCO_3^- , with
149 respiratory CO_2 being an additional source in mollusks (75-81). The proton load
150 generated during calcification is harmful if not removed. All three groups are known to
151 employ transmembrane transport to accomplish proton export ((74) Fig. 3), but
152 differences in the proteins involved may alter their vulnerability to ocean acidification
153 (14). Foraminifers and mollusks use active transport, i.e. a V-ATPase and a $\text{H}^+/\text{Ca}^{2+}$
154 exchanger in foraminifers and Na^+/H^+ exchangers, voltage gated proton channels, and H^+
155 ATPase in mollusks (79, 82-85). Coccolithophores, by contrast, use passive transport
156 through a plasma membrane voltage dependent H^+ channel, which has been shown to
157 break down under acidification (74), potentially limiting their capacity to adapt to changes
158 in seawater carbonate chemistry compared to foraminifers and pteropods. Under ocean
159 acidification the proton motive force would cause a net flux of protons from seawater into
160 the cytosol, but the proton channels close under ocean acidification so that proton flux
161 effectively ceases, and the cytosol acidifies with detrimental consequences for
162 biochemistry (Fig.3).

163
164 The three groups also differ significantly in the processes of calcium transport, shell
165 morphogenesis, and CaCO_3 polymorph (the different crystalline structures in which
166 CaCO_3 can exist) (Fig. 1, Table S1). Coccolithophores and foraminifers produce calcite
167 whereas pteropods produce aragonite. Although aragonite is more soluble than calcite this
168 does not necessarily imply that pteropod shells are more vulnerable than coccoliths or
169 foraminiferal tests (86). Although these distinctions are important, they are likely not the
170 whole story, as ocean acidification has complex indirect effects and there are still open
171 fundamental questions about the processes of shell formation (e.g., (87-89)).

172 173 ● **Oxygen concentration**

174
175 Changes in seawater dissolved oxygen levels are predicted to be one of the most
176 significant impacts of climate change, with much of the surface global ocean expected to
177 experience reduced oxygen (90-94). Deoxygenation is expanding the oxygen minimum
178 zones (OMZs) (95) that are also associated with high productivity eastern boundary
179 upwelling systems. The influence of warming and heatwaves (90-94, 96, 97), thus poses
180 a significant challenge to all three calcifying plankton groups, which all depend on oxygen
181 for respiration. As OMZs are also characterized by low seawater pH they may pose a
182 doubly severe threat for calcifying organisms due to combined effects of deoxygenation
183 and acidification.

184
185 Unicellular organisms, such as coccolithophores and foraminifers, acquire oxygen via
186 diffusion, the rate of which depends on organism size, but does not scale proportionally
187 with the oxygen demands associated with increasing cell size (98). The existence of

188 maximum theoretical cell sizes associated with different oxygen levels (98) suggests that
189 in OMZs the maximum sustainable size for unicellular organisms may fall below the
190 typical size range of certain groups (99). Group-specific adaptation mechanisms may
191 exist, as indicated for example by the fact that in the eastern Pacific OMZ the foraminifer
192 *Globorotaloides hexagona* produces shells that are larger, more porous, less dense, and
193 have more chambers in the final whorl, likely to facilitate gas exchange (100).
194 Multicellular organisms like pteropods employ active mechanisms for oxygen uptake and
195 transport, enabling them to survive in environments with lower oxygen concentrations
196 than would be predicted based solely on surface-area-to-volume ratios (98). Additionally,
197 vertical and latitudinal migration may help mitigate the physiological challenges posed
198 by low-oxygen conditions (52, 58, 101, 102).

199
200 ● ***Warming and nutrient availability***

201
202 Increasing surface ocean temperature directly impacts plankton distribution and
203 productivity by altering cellular processes (e.g., (103-107)) and indirectly through
204 dissolved nutrient availability in the photic zone (108-110). The direct effects of warming
205 on heterotrophic plankton alter metabolic rates, shifts in distribution, and changes in
206 community structure shaping ecosystem responses (e.g., (25, 107)). Future warming
207 could have important implications for coccolithophores, which compete with diatoms and
208 other groups for nutrients required for photosynthesis-driven organic matter production
209 (38, 56). While overall net primary productivity from phytoplankton is projected to
210 decline (110), standing stocks and coccolithophore production may increase at high
211 latitudes, where nutrient limitation is expected to especially suppress competitors like
212 diatoms (111). Conversely, group-specific temperature effects – particularly the greater
213 vulnerability of coccolithophores compared to diazotrophs and diatoms (112) may instead
214 lead to reductions in coccolithophore abundance and productivity. For organisms which
215 harbor photosynthetic symbionts, such as some mixotrophic foraminifers, decreasing
216 nutrient availability is known to impact their distribution, depending on their capacity to
217 alleviate nutrient limitation via phagotrophy (102). For strictly heterotrophic organisms,
218 including pteropods and most foraminifers, nutrients primarily impact their distributions
219 indirectly by influencing the availability of essential food sources (113-115).

220
221 ● ***Predator-prey dynamics***

222
223 In the future ocean, predator-prey dynamics are predicted to be impacted both by changes
224 in nutrient conditions and cascading effects on prey availability. The formulation of
225 predator-prey interactions is one of the largest sources of uncertainty in current CMIP6
226 models (116). For calcifying organisms, size, motility, and trophic strategy are key traits
227 underpinning predator-prey dynamics. Coccolithophores might become more susceptible
228 to grazing due to negative effects of ocean acidification and warming on the integrity of
229 their composite exoskeletons (coccospheres), which comprise elaborate, often
230 interlocking CaCO₃ coccoliths (117). Foraminifers and pteropods are sensitive to prey
231 concentration. Foraminifers, particularly in their prolocular stage, are primarily
232 herbivorous and broaden their dietary sources as they develop, with many spinose species
233 employing their spines to capture larger zooplankton prey (43, 118). This ability to switch
234 from herbivory to carnivory may afford competitive advantage, especially in
235 environments with low phytoplankton concentration and high copepod abundance (119,
236 120). The feeding behavior of pteropods involves deployment of a large mucous web in
237 the water column which captures particles, allowing them to filter substantial amounts of

238 water, providing a competitive advantage when food availability is limited (121-123).
239 Furthermore, the active swimming capability of pteropods (121, 124) means they can
240 actively seek prey and are thus less constrained in their feeding strategy (125).

241

242 There is ongoing debate about the impact of biomineralization state on grazing or
243 predation susceptibility. The large differences in PIC:POC between groups (Fig. 1; Table
244 S1) have been proposed to impact their sensitivities to grazing/predation (18, 21). High
245 PIC:POC is thought to act as a defense mechanism (21, 126), making prey less palatable
246 to predators. However, the role of CaCO₃ in predator protection is still contested, with
247 few studies on foraminifer and pteropod predator sensitivities and no clear advantages of
248 coccolith formation in field observations (127) or laboratory experiments (128).

249

250

251 **Pelagic CaCO₃ production, export, dissolution, and burial**

252

253 Ocean alkalinity exerts a first order control on atmospheric CO₂ (3, 8) and is largely
254 governed by the production, export, dissolution, and burial of CaCO₃ produced by
255 calcifying plankton. Below we assess group-specific contributions to successive stages of
256 the marine CaCO₃ cycle, revealing significant differences in CaCO₃ fate between each
257 group, and highlighting key – often overlooked – processes governing the cycle. While
258 oceanic CaCO₃ production is widely accepted to be a biologically mediated process, we
259 argue that the export and dissolution of CaCO₃ should equally be viewed as such.

260

261 • ***CaCO₃ production versus shallow export production***

262

263 Estimates for total global pelagic CaCO₃ production range from 700-4700 Tg C yr⁻¹ yet
264 underlying this range is a broad spectrum of methods potentially tracking different aspects
265 of production, but usually considered equivalent ((2) and references therein). Contrary to
266 previous work, we separate recent estimates of global CaCO₃ production for each group
267 into those tracking CaCO₃ production and those tracking shallow export production
268 (Fig.4; Table S2; Supplementary Materials).

269

270 Depth integrated production estimates based on living biomass, turnover time (related to
271 the average lifespan of a group), and calcification rate suggest global total CaCO₃
272 production of 1040-3340 Tg C yr⁻¹ (Table S3; Supplementary Materials).
273 Coccolithophores dominate CaCO₃ production (90%), followed by foraminifers (7%) and
274 pteropods (3%) (Fig. 4; Table S3; (7, 16, 129-131)). Pteropods, however, may play a more
275 important role in the polar ocean ((132); Fig. 2). Conversely, estimates of shallow (300-
276 1000 m) export production based on water column chemistry and sediment trap data
277 converge to 680-900 Tg C yr⁻¹ (Fig. 4) (7, 133-135). While total CaCO₃ export is better
278 constrained than total CaCO₃ production, all available measures indicate that production
279 is substantially higher than shallow export (Fig. 4). Depth integrated production estimates
280 contrast with observed biomass distributions of calcifying plankton (Fig 2 D-F), which
281 seem to suggest pteropods and coccolithophores have broadly similar mean biomass
282 concentrations. The large difference between biomass and production is explained by
283 both higher PIC:POC of coccolithophores compared to pteropods (Fig 1) and the
284 considerably higher turnover rates of coccolithophores compared to pteropods. While tiny
285 coccolithophores turnover on the order of days (with considerable variability, Table S1),
286 pteropods are much larger and cycle on the order of several weeks to as low as one per
287 year (Table S1).

288

289 Despite the much larger relative fraction that coccolithophores contribute to total CaCO₃
290 production (on the order of ~2000 Tg C yr⁻¹), all three groups contribute similar fractions
291 to the export flux. Available data suggest that coccolithophores, foraminifers, and
292 pteropods contribute respectively 38%, 42%, and 20% to the total shallow (mesopelagic,
293 200-1000m) export flux (7). These estimates indicate relatively less coccolithophore
294 CaCO₃ in mesopelagic export fluxes compared to total production (epipelagic, 0-200 m),
295 amounting to an excess of coccolithophore production relative to export of over ~1000
296 Tg C yr⁻¹. Although a substantial fraction of non-identified CaCO₃ in many of the
297 compiled sediment-trap studies (e.g.(5, 7)) adds uncertainty to the group-specific
298 contributions to export, this limitation is insufficient to account for the shortfall
299 (Supplemental Material).

300

301 Sediment-based estimates put the contribution of foraminifers and coccolithophores to
302 sediment burial at around 50% each, with a negligible role for pteropods (Fig. 4; (136,
303 137)), again indicating relatively less coccolithophore CaCO₃ compared to their CaCO₃
304 production estimates, and the near complete dissolution of pteropod CaCO₃ in the water
305 column. While considerable uncertainty remains in these estimates, particularly for
306 production, the shallow export of coccolithophore CaCO₃ is substantially (~80%) lower
307 than total coccolithophore CaCO₃ production using all available measures. In contrast,
308 shallow export fluxes of foraminifers and pteropods, appear higher than estimates of total
309 production (Fig. 4; Table S2). This apparent 'missing' production by foraminifers and
310 pteropods is most likely due to a low bias in their production estimates (16), as there is
311 no obvious mechanism for export to exceed production. Given the considerable
312 uncertainty in pteropod turnover time (from weeks to years, Table S1), a shorter turnover
313 time of several weeks, as opposed to the value of one year used by Knecht et al. (16),
314 could bring the pteropod production and export values into closer agreement. This
315 considerable uncertainty in the turnover time of pteropods remains a key source of
316 uncertainty in estimates of their CaCO₃ production. It is not possible to reach such
317 agreement between the production and export values of foraminifers using reasonable
318 estimates of turnover time, pointing to further biases in the underlying biomass data (16).

319

320 The difference between total coccolithophore CaCO₃ production, export (and
321 underrepresentation in sediment burial) may reflect an overestimation of their total
322 CaCO₃ production. Yet, coccolithophore CaCO₃ production can be determined by
323 satellite images and algorithms, due to the unique optical properties of the
324 coccoliths (130, 138, 139), making coccolithophore CaCO₃ production better constrained
325 compared to that of foraminifers and pteropods. Although satellite production estimates
326 may be susceptible to biases (Supplementary Materials, (130, 139)) particularly in poor
327 retrieval regions such as the Southern Ocean (140), the agreement between the two
328 commonly used satellite-based algorithms, which have markedly different
329 methodologies, argues against this. Furthermore, simpler extrapolation approaches that
330 do not rely on satellite data arrive at similar (141), or substantially higher (2, 142, 143)
331 estimates of global coccolithophore CaCO₃ production (Supplementary Materials).
332 Consequently, the very high values of coccolithophore CaCO₃ production appear to be a
333 robust feature of the data, rather than an artifact of methodological bias.

334

335 ● ***Widespread shallow dissolution of coccolithophore CaCO₃***

336

337 The difference between production and export of CaCO₃ can instead be explained by
338 substantial dissolution of coccolithophore CaCO₃ in the upper ocean. Contrary to the
339 ‘canonical’ view of deep CaCO₃ dissolution (e.g. (8, 144)), water column dissolution
340 estimates show that highest CaCO₃ dissolution rates are in fact in the upper few hundred
341 meters of the water column, far above the calcite (and aragonite) saturation horizon (Fig.
342 4; (133, 134, 145-147)). This shallow dissolution is observed in every basin (133, 134,
343 147), with studies suggesting between 12-90% of exported CaCO₃ dissolves in the upper
344 ~1000 m (133, 134, 146, 148-150). The recent study of Kwon et al. (147) further indicates
345 ~40% of CaCO₃ dissolves in the upper 300m, with the most intensive dissolution at the
346 base of the euphotic zone in areas of high primary productivity (147).

347
348 Modeling studies demonstrate that a high-production high-dissolution regime best
349 explains seawater alkalinity and sediment trap CaCO₃ flux data from the upper ocean
350 (135, 147, 151). Furthermore, substantial shallow dissolution of coccolithophore CaCO₃
351 has been observed directly during blooms (152). Evidence for much of this shallow
352 dissolution comprising coccolithophore CaCO₃ comes from three main sources. First,
353 comparison of *in situ* production and shallow export rates in the North Pacific show
354 coccolithophore CaCO₃ production is far higher than export (2). Second, comparison of
355 coccolithophore assemblages in standing stocks versus shallow export flux demonstrates
356 that smaller and less-calcified species are lost from the export flux. This is likely due to
357 species-specific selective dissolution (e.g., (153, 154) (Fig.5)). Finally, the highest
358 correlation between CaCO₃ and POC attenuation within the upper ocean occurs within
359 the smallest particle size class, consistent with that of coccolithophores (1-50 μm) (147,
360 155).

361
362 The fate of CaCO₃ in the ocean thus appears to vary between the different groups:
363 foraminifers are relatively efficient at exporting CaCO₃ to both the mesopelagic and
364 sediment, whereas coccolithophores appear to be inefficient CaCO₃ exporters compared
365 to their total production, although still constitute a major contributor to CaCO₃ burial (Fig.
366 4). The case is less clear for pteropods, with available data suggesting that they export
367 CaCO₃ relatively efficiently from the upper ocean, although their aragonite shells dissolve
368 within the water column and at the sediment-seawater interface, and are thus rarely
369 preserved in sediments.

370
371 ● ***CaCO₃ export production and dissolution as ecosystem-modulated processes***
372

373 We are left with two key questions: i) what are the factors and processes which determine
374 whether CaCO₃ is exported to depth or dissolved within the upper ocean? and, ii) what
375 drives the different export efficiencies of the calcifying groups? For insight, we should
376 consider how dissolution occurs in the upper ocean. The dissolution of calcite and
377 aragonite in the upper few hundred meters, where seawater is supersaturated with respect
378 to these minerals, requires widespread biologically mediated dissolution (133, 145, 147,
379 156, 157). Such biologically mediated dissolution is required to match water column
380 dissolution patterns regardless of the proportion of calcite or aragonite exported (145,
381 147, 151, 157).

382
383 Biologically-mediated respiration comprises both respiration-driven dissolution in
384 particle microenvironments (155, 157-160), possibly including respiration of the POC
385 associated with calcifying organisms themselves (136, 152, 161), and gut-digestion
386 following grazing or predation (158, 162-164). Dean et al. (158) showed that

387 microzooplankton grazing dissolves ~90% of ingested coccolithophore calcite, and could
388 explain 50-100% of the observed CaCO₃ dissolution in supersaturated waters (158). The
389 equivalence of turnover times for coccolithophore CaCO₃ and soft tissue suggests that
390 their removal from the upper ocean is controlled by similar (i.e. biological) processes
391 (142). Crucially, the processes of particle aggregation and fecal pellet production
392 following predation are also thought to play a key role in CaCO₃ export (2, 158, 165). As
393 such, the different export efficiencies of calcifying plankton groups will largely be
394 controlled by how their different physiological, ecological, and behavioral traits of each
395 group interact with these ecosystem processes (Fig. 1; Table S1). We briefly discuss the
396 most relevant of these traits and their ecosystem interactions below:

397
398 - **Size** is likely the most important trait difference between the calcifying groups in
399 terms of export efficiency as it determines particle sinking speed. While adult
400 foraminifers and pteropods are mostly sand-grain sized and can sink rapidly after death
401 (80-1500 m day⁻¹, 43-1200 m day⁻¹, respectively; (43, 124, 166)), coccoliths are much
402 smaller and typically do not sink individually ((0-2.4 m day⁻¹); (167, 168)) unless
403 packaged in aggregates (e.g., marine snow) and/or faecal pellets (167). This necessitates
404 association of their CaCO₃ with large amounts of POC, the respiration of which can drive
405 micro-environmental undersaturation, promoting dissolution (145, 157-160) (Fig.4).

406 - **PIC:POC** is variable and highly dependent on the amount of POC within the
407 bodies of the calcifying plankton groups. Respiration of this POC following death may
408 promote self-dissolution (136, 152, 161) and PIC:POC may also be important in
409 determining predation rates (see section *Predator-prey dynamics*). Foraminifers contain
410 relatively less POC compared to pteropods and coccolithophores, although PIC:POC
411 varies widely between species in the latter (169).

412 - **Motility** may influence predation risk, with reduced motility increasing predator
413 encounter rates (170, 171). Furthermore, vertical migration can lead to more efficient PIC
414 export (165). While coccolithophores have limited motility, some species of pteropods
415 are strong swimmers, capable of relatively large diel migration (Fig. 4), and both they and
416 foraminifers can undertake ontogenetic vertical migrations of several hundred meters
417 (124).

418 - **Mineralogy** Considering seawater chemistry alone, aragonite becomes
419 thermodynamically unstable shallower in the water column than calcite (172). However,
420 the 'metabolic' saturation state (the saturation state of calcite and aragonite given complete
421 respiration of the oxygen within a water parcel and Redfield stoichiometry) can promote
422 calcite to dissolve faster than aragonite in the upper water-column (157). In addition,
423 foraminiferal and coccolithophore calcite has been shown to dissolve at different rates
424 given the same degree of undersaturation (157). This suggests that group-specific
425 microstructure, arising from their varied biomineralisation strategies, may also play an
426 important role (86) (see *Ocean acidification and biomineralization*).

427
428 Compared to foraminifers and pteropods, coccolithophores are very small, with limited
429 mobility, and low individual sinking rate, making them prone to shallow water
430 dissolution. Additionally, the low PIC:POC of some coccolithophore species further
431 increases the vulnerability of these species to shallow dissolution, thereby reducing their
432 CaCO₃ export efficiency (Table S1, Fig. 1).

433

434 Given that a large amount of coccolithophore calcite appears to dissolve in the upper
435 ocean, assessing the main processes that regulate this mechanism will be key to
436 understanding (and modeling) how alkalinity is cycled through the ocean, how CaCO₃
437 export is likely to change in the future with climate change (11), and how it may have
438 changed in the geological past (see *Calcifying plankton in the geological record*). As with
439 the biological carbon pump (173), it seems that the structure and dynamics of the whole
440 ecosystem matters, with differing dynamics driving different CaCO₃ export efficiencies
441 (147, 165). Therefore, it is essential to move beyond the potential effects of ocean
442 acidification on primary calcification and consider the broader impact of climate change
443 on all ecosystem processes that regulate shallow dissolution and CaCO₃ export.
444

446 **Calcifying plankton in the geological record**

447
448 Modern estimates of organism size (Fig. 1) and global distributions of diversity (Fig. 2)
449 do not illustrate the variation and change these organisms have exhibited over geological
450 time scales (Fig. 5). Both body size and diversity show large fluctuations through time
451 (Fig. 5), likely as a response to acidification and warming during past atmospheric CO₂
452 changes. Whether or not this represents heritable plasticity will help to infer how future
453 environmental change may alter body size and many other closely correlated traits (Fig.
454 1).

455
456 Pelagic biomineralization of CaCO₃ has been continuous since the evolution of
457 coccolithophores in the Late Triassic (225 Ma) (174), followed by planktonic
458 foraminifers in the Jurassic (170 Ma) (175), and pteropods in the mid Cretaceous (125Ma)
459 (176, 177). Biomineralization in pelagic waters has caused a shift of the primary loci of
460 carbonate sedimentation from the shelves to the open ocean, resulting in accumulation of
461 thick CaCO₃ sediments across vast areas of the world ocean. Subduction of these
462 carbonates has fundamentally changed the global carbon cycle (3, 4, 178). Given recent
463 developments in understanding controls on production, diversity, and cycling of
464 calcifying plankton within the modern ocean, we revisit key trends from the geological
465 record. Fossil studies of calcifying plankton tend to assume that primary production and
466 species diversity dominate pelagic sedimentary carbonate accumulation (Fig. 5C) and
467 species diversity change (Fig. 5G) above the carbonate compensation depth (CCD; Fig.
468 5D). However, as highlighted above, there is growing evidence that shallow water
469 dissolution is a major biogeochemical process, which modulates export fluxes and
470 possibly biases the ocean sedimentary record.

471
472 As planktonic foraminifers appear to be relatively little affected by shallow water
473 dissolution – with export flux being a significant proportion of their CaCO₃ production
474 (2, 16)– the foraminiferal fossil record in surface sediments closely reflects surface
475 plankton populations (179). Conversely, coccolithophore export fluxes are only a small
476 proportion of their production and sedimentary fossil assemblages are heavily biased
477 toward taxa which produce larger and more robust coccoliths (153, 154). Finally, the
478 pteropod fossil record is very limited and patchy due to dissolution in the water column,
479 on the seafloor, and during early diagenesis (180). This selective dissolution is reflected
480 in the comparison of the diversity of extant species in the plankton and in the Holocene
481 sediment record (Fig. 5 G). Recognition of the importance of water column dissolution
482 suggests that re-evaluation of the long-term history of pelagic carbonate production in the
483 fossil record is needed, particularly as the biogeochemical, physiological, and ecological

484 factors driving shallow dissolution are susceptible to significant change over geological
485 timescales.

486

487 ● ***Ecological bias in the fossil record***

488 The same overlooked shallow dissolution altering the balance of global fluxes is also
489 likely biasing the fossil record. If we assume that prior ages had a similar relative fraction
490 of production that was dissolved before reaching the sediment as we observe today (Fig.
491 4), we can deduce that the vast majority of less calcified shelled planktonic organisms are
492 absent from the fossil record. Measures of historical- and geological-scale diversity
493 within different groups are commonly used to infer their ecological significance and
494 possible reactions to environmental change (Fig. 5 G) (e.g. (154, 177, 181-183)). However,
495 significant methodological challenges remain in compiling diversity distributions (e.g.,
496 (184)) and in unraveling the causal pathways behind observed correlations with
497 environmental change.

498 Geological diversity measures will also underrate groups that are more prone to
499 dissolution, further biasing and complicating the deep-time picture. One striking example
500 of the fossil record giving a biased view of ecological reality is provided by the earliest
501 known planktonic foraminifers: the Conoglobigerinidae, first observed in the Middle
502 Jurassic to the Early Cretaceous (175). Since this group is rare and poorly known, it has
503 been assumed that they are also ecologically and biogeochemically unimportant.
504 However, it is now known that their shells were originally aragonitic (175) so the poor
505 record may have largely been a function of preservation rather than original abundance
506 and CaCO₃ production. Similarly, the limited fossil record of pteropods has almost
507 certainly resulted in under-appreciation of their ecological and biogeochemical roles at
508 the geological timescale.

509

510 ● ***Pelagic biocalcification crises: dissolution driven?***

511 Many of the best-documented intervals of abrupt environmental change in the fossil
512 record are marked by sediments with reduced CaCO₃ content and increased organic
513 carbon content (185, 186). In the Mesozoic the prime examples are the Oceanic Anoxic
514 Events (OAEs) of the Early Toarcian, the basal Aptian (OAE1a) and Cenomanian
515 Turonian boundary (OAE2) (185). Subsequently the Cretaceous-Paleogene boundary and
516 the Paleocene Eocene Thermal Maximum are also marked by sediments with major
517 reductions in CaCO₃ content. These intervals have frequently been described as
518 "calcification crises", with the assumption that reduced accumulation of pelagic carbonate
519 was primarily driven by reduced production of pelagic CaCO₃ due to inhibition of
520 calcification in surface waters, possibly linked to ocean acidification. This view was
521 questioned by the discovery by Slater et al. (187) of impressions of well-formed
522 nanofossils in organic matter from the most organic-rich levels of several OAEs. These
523 intervals had been interpreted as periods of severe environmental change during which
524 calcification was inhibited, but evidently these were, partly, intervals of differential
525 preservation. More generally, it is necessary to account for the full balance of export
526 production, including variable water-column dissolution, production, dilution, and early
527 diagenetic dissolution. This balance would help to evaluate the significance of intervals
528 of reduced pelagic CaCO₃ accumulation, possibly due to changes in size and mass, species
529 PIC:POC, productivity, and/or changes in ocean alkalinity rather than assuming that they
530 represent "calcification crises" (e.g. Fig. 5 C, e.g., (188-190)).

531

532 ● ***Reduced CaCO₃ accumulation in the Plio-Pleistocene***

533 Quaternary and Holocene calcareous nannofossil assemblages (mainly coccolithophore
534 fossils) are typically dominated by small coccoliths (3-5 μm in size) (e.g. (191, 192)).
535 This is in marked contrast both to earlier fossil assemblages which typically are
536 dominated by larger coccoliths (5-10 μm in size) (Fig. 5 F) (193) and to modern plankton
537 assemblages in which coccolithophores with significantly smaller coccoliths (<3 μm in
538 size) often dominate (154). During the Quaternary and Holocene, in contrast, planktonic
539 foraminiferal size is unchanged (high latitudes) or increased (low latitudes) (Fig. 5 E)
540 (194), suggesting that different drivers regulate their size, and that they are less affected
541 by water column dissolution.

542

543 The virtual absence of smaller coccoliths in modern sediments is largely a result of
544 dissolution in the water column. Small coccoliths such as those produced by
545 Syracosphaeraceae and Rhabdosphaeraceae are largely absent, even from settling
546 assemblages in deep sediment traps (153, 154). Conversely, the absence of larger
547 coccoliths is the result of an evolutionary effect since large and heavily calcified genera
548 have become extinct, rather than less abundant (174). Sucheras-Marx and Henderiks
549 (195) conducted a detailed study of this Pliocene-Pleistocene size reduction from five
550 deep sea drilling sites from the Atlantic, Pacific and Indian Oceans. They showed that
551 size reduction coincided with a reduction of 50% or more in the overall pelagic carbonate
552 sedimentation rate (196) (Fig. 5 C, F and references therein) in the absence of changes in
553 atmospheric CO₂ concentration, surface seawater pH and reconstructed CCD (Fig. 5 A,
554 B, D). A similar size reduction is not seen in planktonic foraminifers (Fig. 5 E) and the
555 data (195) suggest that the reduction in carbonate accumulation rates is primarily driven
556 by reduced coccolithophore carbonate flux, whilst foraminiferal carbonate flux was
557 essentially unchanged (Fig. 5 C).

558

559 The change in the foraminifer to coccolith CaCO₃ ratio from production to sedimentary
560 record is also widely supported by evidence from sediment traps and surface sediments.
561 This ratio is near 1:1 in modern sediments (Fig. 4; (137)), which is abnormally high by
562 comparison with most pre-Pliocene pelagic sediments where a ratio of 1:10 or 1:20 is
563 typical (Fig. 5 C, references therein). The shift to smaller coccolith size in the fossil record
564 will almost certainly reflect the increased rate of water column dissolution of the
565 coccolithophore population. It is possible that reduced size alone drove flux reduction
566 without a necessary surface production reduction. The fact that size reduction in
567 coccolithophores occurs without any parallel effect in planktonic foraminifers suggests
568 this is not driven by calcification inhibition, but rather by selection for smaller coccolith
569 size.

570

571 One likely driver of reduction in coccolith size is increased water column stratification,
572 leading to selection for lighter, slower sinking cells which can remain in suspension (21,
573 195). In parallel, there is evidence of increased stratification from development of the
574 deep photic assemblage of both planktonic foraminifers and coccolithophores (197).
575 Longer term coccolith size reduction through the Cenozoic (the last 66.0 Ma) is more
576 likely linked to CO₂ reduction (198-200) (Fig. 5 A, F). Irrespective of cause, an effect of
577 reduced coccolith size would have been greater dissolution in the upper water column,
578 leading to less efficient CaCO₃ export, higher surface alkalinity, and potentially lower
579 atmospheric CO₂.

580

581

582 **Future research directions**

583

584 Despite the importance of oceanic CaCO₃ production and export there are still major
585 uncertainties in our estimates of the different contributors, with shallow dissolution
586 particularly poorly constrained. Recognition of uncertainties highlights several key
587 directions for future research. For group-specific stock estimates, metabarcoding data
588 could significantly increase data coverage, once suitable genomic markers have been
589 identified and algorithms have been developed to reliably convert genetic marker
590 frequency data into carbon stock estimates (201, 202). To quantify group-specific water
591 column CaCO₃ production and export efficiency, *in situ* methods providing seasonal
592 datasets would be invaluable. For larger organisms such as pteropods and foraminifers
593 imaging devices such as the Underwater Vision Profiler (UVP) and the In Situ
594 Ichthyoplankton Imaging System (ISIIS) combined with automated image recognition is
595 a promising method (203).

596

597 Changes of alkalinity from shallow CaCO₃ dissolution are often masked by mixing (short
598 residence time of surface waters) and biological processes (e.g., photosynthesis,
599 respiration, nitrate uptake) altering parts of the carbonate system (like dissolved inorganic
600 carbon and pH)(204). Rapid mixing disperses the alkalinity signature of localized CaCO₃
601 dissolution before it can be clearly detected, especially over the timescales typical of
602 sampling. Shallow sediment trap time-series and *in situ* optical and chemical sensors can
603 directly measure sinking particles and CaCO₃ flux, providing targeted, group-specific
604 insights into the extent and location of dissolution, and its relationship to POC attenuation
605 (133, 147, 160). Shallow flux data could also be integrated using Argo floats (7).
606 Mechanistic understanding of shallow water dissolution could be advanced by
607 experiments addressing the driving processes (e.g., grazing, predation, aggregation) (155,
608 Fig. 4). Methodologically, employing isotope tracers (such as ¹³C and ⁴⁴Ca) to identify
609 biomineral-specific dissolution rates and pathways in natural environments can be highly
610 effective. (145, 158).

611

612 Future climate impacts on calcifying plankton are likely to be multi-variate and group-
613 specific, yet current CMIP models rely on implicit representations of calcification (11)
614 that cannot capture these differences. Advancing the realism and mechanistic resolution
615 of models will require explicit inclusion of the three major calcifying groups and
616 classification of functional types based on key ecological traits such as predation defense
617 (38, 111, 205), heterotrophy (18, 135) and mixotrophy (205), carbonate chemistry
618 sensitivity (111, 206), and thermal preference (38, 111, 206). Models should also
619 incorporate currently overlooked mechanisms such as mixotrophy for coccolithophores,
620 oxygen requirements for pteropods and foraminifers, and vertical migration for
621 pteropods. Field and experimental science is key to develop next-generation models
622 equipped to capture the trait-driven, group-specific, responses to future ocean conditions
623 (207).

624

625 Research on pelagic carbonate production in Earth history would benefit from further
626 exploration of the extensive archive of cores from deep sea drilling, which remains poorly
627 synthesized (Fig. 5). Synthesizing group specific accumulation rates from this large body
628 of data should be a prime target for the developing IODP-cubed program (International
629 Ocean Drilling Programme-3) (208). When combined with paleo-oceanographic models
630 that can explicitly represent calcifying plankton functional types (205), these data could

631 be used to study the mechanisms controlling pelagic carbonate accumulation through
632 time. Furthermore, such data could be used to validate modelled response during past
633 variations in atmospheric CO₂ and climate (205).

634

635 **Conclusion**

636

637 Anthropogenic carbon emissions not only drive ocean acidification, but also affect a wide
638 array of biogeochemical parameters relevant to calcifying plankton. These include ocean
639 warming, nutrient cycling and species distribution, prey availability, and oxygen
640 concentrations across local to global scales (e.g., (108, 110, 209)). Impacts will vary
641 between calcifying plankton groups and be spatially heterogeneous due to differences in
642 group-specific traits and responses to environmental changes (Fig. 1, Table S1).

643

644 The influences of climate change are highly multi-variate and group-specific, such that
645 quantifying specific effects remains challenging. However, laboratory experiments,
646 mesocosms, meta-analysis, and modeling efforts indicate a general reduction of
647 biodiversity of the three groups by the end of this century (e.g. (25, 210-214)). Given
648 biodiversity's pivotal role in stability and ecosystem functioning (215-217), there is a need
649 to deepen our understanding of the mechanisms driving biodiversity in current and future
650 oceans to protect biodiversity and strengthen the resilience of marine ecosystems against
651 rapid environmental change.

652 In terms of group-specific vulnerability to climate change, the oxygenation state of
653 ambient seawater could possibly have the least impact on small autotrophic
654 coccolithophores, while larger heterotrophic organisms like pteropods and foraminifers
655 will likely be most affected due to higher metabolic oxygen requirements (e.g. (54, 55,
656 218, 219)). Shoaling of the mixed layer may disproportionately impact organisms
657 confined to the photic zone, such as coccolithophores. Nutrient availability and prey
658 quality alterations could have cascading effects on trophic dynamics within marine
659 ecosystems, affecting the abundance and distribution of these planktonic species. Finally,
660 while acidification will impact calcifying plankton, the different biomineralization
661 strategies of the groups is likely to modulate their sensitivity. The absence of active proton
662 pumps in coccolithophores may make them particularly susceptible to increasing
663 seawater proton concentrations (ocean acidification).

664 Comparing CaCO₃ production, shallow export, and burial fluxes reveals different fates of
665 the CaCO₃ produced by each group, likely linked to their size, motility, PIC:POC, and
666 mineralogy (Fig. 1; Table S1). Coccolithophores dominate CaCO₃ production, however
667 much of this CaCO₃ appears to be dissolved in shallow waters via poorly understood
668 biologically-mediated processes. Dissolution (157, 158) in the upper water column is a
669 much more important process than has been typically assumed when interpreting the
670 geological record, and re-interpretation of the degree to which fossil assemblages of
671 coccolithophores and pteropods reflect changing biodiversity is warranted. We suggest
672 that a reduction in coccolith size has changed upper water column dissolution and CaCO₃
673 export efficiency over the late Cenozoic, which in turn may have driven the observed
674 reduction in pelagic carbonate mass accumulation rates. Such deep-time observations
675 highlight the potential of biologically-mediated processes to contribute to oceanic
676 alkalinity and atmospheric CO₂ change. Modeling these factors may improve predictions
677 and facilitate more resolved understanding of the global carbon cycle, both past and
678 future.

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- 1591

1592 **Figure captions**

1593

1594 **Figure 1. Main calcifying plankton groups and their key traits.** (A-C) Scanning
1595 Electron Microscopy (SEM) images of representative species: (A) Coccolithophore
1596 (*Gephyrocapsa ericsonii*), (B) Foraminifer (*Globigerina bulloides*), and (C) Pteropod
1597 (*Limacina helicina*). (D-I) Trait-specific differences and their ecological significance: (D)
1598 Organism size spans four orders of magnitude, affecting prey capture and requirements
1599 for nutrients and oxygen. (E) The ratio of inorganic to organic carbon (PIC:POC) varies
1600 among groups, with higher ratios linked to greater sensitivity to pH due to increased
1601 proton loads. (F) Motility ranges widely (2–3 orders of magnitude), with highly motile
1602 groups like pteropods requiring more energy and oxygen than less motile
1603 coccolithophores and foraminifers. (G) Photosynthetic capacity influencing the need for
1604 light and nutrients. (H) Calcification sites differ, with extracellular calcification (e.g.,
1605 pteropods and foraminifers) potentially showing lower sensitivity to seawater pH changes
1606 than coccolithophores. (I) Nutritional strategies differ; coccolithophores primarily
1607 depend on photosynthesis (autotrophy or mixotrophy), whereas pteropods and
1608 foraminifers rely entirely on predation (heterotrophy). For additional traits and references,
1609 see Table S1. SEM images by Jeremy Young. Color ribbons show the range of specific
1610 traits for each group (D, E, F). Gray scale ribbons show the relative group sensitivity to
1611 specific trait (darker color reflects higher sensitivity).

1612

1613 **Figure 2. Biomass and diversity trends of the three main calcifying plankton groups.**
1614 Latitudinal diversity (Shannon index) distribution (A-C) and, biomass latitudinal and
1615 depth profiles (D-I) for coccolithophores (A, D, G), planktonic foraminifers (B, E, H),
1616 and shelled pteropods (C, F, I). Shaded areas indicate 95% confidence intervals. Total
1617 carbon data for D–F include samples collected using both plankton nets and multineets,
1618 while G–I exclusively use multinet data (upper 800m) (See Supplementary Material).
1619 Some pteropod species can be found at depths > 800 meters, although this is relatively
1620 rare and the biomass at this depth is mainly made of postmortem sinking specimens
1621 (Figure S1) (e.g. (220)). Data sources: (A, C) (CASCADE) (221), (D, F); (FORCIS)
1622 (222), (G, I); (16) and (Species Distribution Model) (24), (B, E, H).

1623

1624 **Figure 3. Schematic of calcification-related pH regulation mechanisms.** The
1625 formation of CaCO_3 generates a proton load in the site of calcification. These protons
1626 have to be removed from the site of calcification and transported into the surrounding
1627 seawater. Since all sites of calcification are membrane-bound and protons do not cross
1628 the lipid bilayer, membrane proteins are required to transport protons. In coccolithophores
1629 (A), protons that leave the coccolith vesicle need to cross the cytoplasm and then the
1630 plasma-membrane. Coccolithophores use plasma-membrane proton channels which form
1631 a proton permeable pore through which protons diffuse along the electrochemical gradient
1632 (“PMF”, proton motive force). In foraminifers (B) and pteropods (C) active proton
1633 transporters use energy (ATP, Adenosine triphosphate and ADP, adenosine diphosphate)
1634 and can therefore transport protons against the electrochemical gradient enabling
1635 foraminifers and pteropods to export protons also under ocean acidification. The usage of

1636 an active, as opposed to a passive, mode of proton removal might put coccolithophores at
1637 a disadvantage under ocean acidification, compared to foraminifers and pteropods.

1638

1639 **Figure 4. The differing fates of biogenic CaCO₃.** (A) Schematic of coccolithophore,
1640 foraminiferal, and pteropod CaCO₃ annual total production, export, water column
1641 dissolution and burial (Table S2). Water depth profile and processes driving CaCO₃
1642 sinking and shallow water dissolution are indicated (pictograms). Dashed boxes show the
1643 discrepancy between estimates of foraminiferal and pteropod CaCO₃ production and its
1644 shallow export, possibly due to a low bias in these production estimates (16). (B) Globally
1645 depth integrated water-column (dark grey) PIC dissolution estimates (133) and sediment
1646 (light grey) CaCO₃ dissolution estimates (204, 223, 224). The globally averaged depth of
1647 the calcite and aragonite saturation horizons with $\pm 1\sigma$ uncertainty is shown by the dashed
1648 and dotted lines, respectively (133). The y-axis scale on panel (B) does not apply precisely
1649 to panel (A). All units are globally integrated Tg C yr⁻¹ (See Supplementary Materials for
1650 more details).

1651

1652 **Figure 5: Geological record of calcifying planktonic groups.** (A) Atmospheric CO₂
1653 (yellow) and (B) pH (pink) reconstructed from boron isotopes (circles) and alkenone
1654 estimates (triangles) (225). (C) Mass accumulation rates of carbonate sediments (dark
1655 brown) and their main producers, coccolithophores (light brown) and planktonic
1656 foraminifers (black), expressed via a GAM fit with 95% confidence intervals
1657 (transparent ribbon), using data from six shallow sites (590, 607, 806, 982, 1264,
1658 U1338) with minimal dissolution effects (196). (D) Equatorial Pacific Carbonate
1659 Compensation Depth (CCD): observed (light purple line, (226)) and model-adjusted
1660 (yellow line with 95% CI, (227) model TX2007 V1). (E) 1-Ma means of planktonic
1661 foraminiferal test size_{95/5} (size separating the largest 5% from the rest of the
1662 assemblage) for low (black) and high (blue) latitudes (228). (F) Coccolith assemblage
1663 size (CAS-90: size of the 10% largest species) in low (red) and high (brown) latitudes
1664 (193). (G) Species richness records for pteropods (green; (177)), coccolithophores
1665 (orange; (183)), and planktonic foraminifers (blue; from (181) >1.5 Ma; from (229) for
1666 surface sediments). Circles show modern species richness from (43, 154, 177, 230).
1667 Grey bands indicate the Cretaceous–Paleogene boundary (K–Pg), Paleocene–Eocene
1668 Thermal Maximum (PETM), and Plio–Pleistocene boundary.
1669

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1683 N.K., W.G., I.A.H., C.M., S.C., J.d.V., R.S., J.R.Y., S.P., R.N., M.G.; Writing – review & editing:
1684 P.Z., G.L., N.K., W.G., I.A.H., C.M., S.C., J.d.V., R.S., J.R.Y., S.P., R.N., S.Z., G.A.-O., S.B.,
1685 T.d.G-T., M.G., A.L., I.P., P.G.M. **Data and materials availability:** All data supporting the
1686 conclusions of this study are provided within the main text and/or the Supplementary Materials.
1687 The datasets used in this review are publicly available through public repositories. Data for
1688 coccolithophores were obtained from the CASCADE dataset (de Vries et al. (221), available at
1689 Zenodo (231), for planktonic foraminifers from the FORCIS database (Chaabane et al., (222),
1690 available at Zenodo (232), and for pteropods from Knecht et al., (16, 233). Additionally, species
1691 distribution model outputs used to examine latitudinal diversity trends were sourced from
1692 Benedetti et al. ((24), available at Zenodo (234). All datasets are openly accessible, and any
1693 derived data or scripts used for figure generation are available from the corresponding author
1694 upon reasonable request.
1695

Figure 1

Figure 2

A

ONLY PASSIVE TRANSPORT
VIA CHANNEL

Present | Acidification

Present:

Passive proton expulsion through open channels.

Acidification:

Channel closed. No expulsion of protons which accumulate in cytoplasm.

B

ACTIVE TRANSPORT VIA
TRANSPORTERS

Present | Acidification

Present:

Active transport of proton expulsion through plasma membrane.

Acidification:

Transporters in plasma-membrane.
Expulsion of protons possible.
More costly (ATP) due to proton gradient.

C

ACTIVE TRANSPORT VIA
TRANSPORTERS

Present | Acidification

Present:

Active transport of proton expulsion through plasma membrane.

Acidification:

Transporters in plasma-membrane.
Expulsion of protons possible.
More costly (ATP) due to proton gradient.

Figure 3

Figure 4

Figure 5

Supplementary Materials for

Calcifying plankton: from biomineralization to global change

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The PDF file includes:

Supplementary Text
Figure S1
Tables S1 to S3
References (235-342)

Supplementary Text

1. **Biomass and diversity patterns of the three calcifying plankton groups**

1.1. **Data acquisition**

To investigate biomass distributions of each plankton group (Figure 2), the most recent datasets available were retrieved from public repositories: coccolithophore data were retrieved from the CASCADE database ((221) <https://zenodo.org/records/13919902>), foraminiferal data from the FORCIS database ((222) <https://zenodo.org/records/12724286>), and pteropod data from ((16) <https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.957258>).

Data sources include coccolithophores ((221) CASCADE), planktonic foraminifers ((222) FORCIS), and shelled pteropods (16) for biomass, and diversity of the three groups ((24) species distribution model).

1.2. **Data pre-processing**

- **Coccolithophore datasets**

For coccolithophores (CASCADE), species-specific estimates of organic carbon (OC) and inorganic carbon (IC) concentrations were combined to estimate total carbon concentrations. These estimates were aggregated across each location (latitude, longitude, depth, day, month and year). This dataset was then used to investigate latitudinal biomass distribution, presented as box plots across latitude (Fig 2D), and latitude vs. depth plots to explore vertical distribution (Fig 2G).

- **Foraminifer datasets**

Foraminifer counts from the FORCIS database were converted to absolute abundance and standardized at a mesh size of 100 μm (235), then converted to species-specific total carbon biomass following methods described in (236). Total carbon was then estimated by summing species-specific estimates for each location (latitude, longitude, depth, day, month and year). To plot the latitudinal distribution of biomass (Fig. 2E), we utilized data collected via plankton nets and multinet from the FORCIS database. Initially, the dataset was filtered to include only samples from the top 200 m, as this is where most living foraminifers are found ((42, 43). This subset allowed us to explore latitudinal patterns effectively. For plotting vertical biomass distribution (Fig. 2H), we relied on multinet samples from the upper 800 m, since plankton nets, while useful, do not accurately resolve depth distributions and often integrate over a large depth range.

- **Pteropod datasets**

Raw data for pteropods from (16) were filtered to only include data from multinet and biomass-resolving sampling devices, labelled as “multi-net” or “other” in the dataset. Latitudinal biomass box plots (Fig 2F) included all sampling methods, while latitude vs. depth plots (Fig 2I) used only multinet data to ensure depth resolution. In Figure 2 we only plot data above 800 meters, as most pteropods are found in the epipelagic and upper mesopelagic zones—but few species can occur alive at depths of 500–800 m (seasonal or ontogenetic migration into the mesopelagic-dormancy/overwintering, (124, 237). Pteropods found at depth >1000 are mainly a result of postmortem passive sinking or less likely vertical transport from strong downwelling currents. Nonetheless, for completeness, the full dataset is included in Figure S1.

1.3. Data processing

After dataset-specific pre-processing, zero values were dropped from each dataset, outliers — defined as values exceeding 1.5 times the interquartile range (IQR) above the third quartile (Q3) or below the first quartile (Q1) (238, 239)— were removed, and data were gridded. For latitudinal box plots, 10-degree latitude bins were used. For coccolithophore latitude vs depth plots, depth bins were gridded to 50 m bins, while for pteropods and foraminifers multi-net depths were used. For each bin, mean values were then calculated using Numpy (240) and plotted using seaborn (241) and matplotlib (242).

Data diversity trends

Latitudinal diversity trends were derived from species distribution model outputs of Benedetti et al., ((24); <https://zenodo.org/records/5101518>). Data were gridded to 10-degree latitude bins and then randomly resampled 1,000 times for each latitude bin to compute mean diversity and 95% confidence intervals using Numpy ((240); Fig. 2). Resulting summary statistics were then plotted using matplotlib (242).

1.4. Data limitations

All databases used represent a significant effort in compiling and unifying data from diverse sources and provide an invaluable foundation for advancing our understanding of the ecology and role in marine ecosystems of calcifying plankton. However, as with any large-scale datasets, certain limitations are inherent. For clarity we list and discuss general data limitations below:

- Spatial-temporal biases are inherent in these datasets, including: 1) Basin specific biases where sampling effort is disproportionately concentrated in one or more basins, such as much higher sampling effort in the Atlantic Ocean compared to other ocean basins. 2) Seasonal biases, with high latitudes not sampled in winter months due to ship-imposed weather constraints. 3) Depth biases, with for instance coccolithophores primarily sampled above 200 meters, when some studies suggest coccolithophore species can be found as deep as 300 meters. 4) Bloom biases, where sampling efforts focus on regions known to have high calcifier plankton stocks based on satellite signals or previous sampling efforts.
- Spatial-temporal heterogeneity significantly influences mean and median biomass estimates due to mesoscale features and short-lasting (or the order of days to weeks) bloom events. Such heterogeneity thus leads to large biomass ranges, and can also lead to “outlier” values which are not necessarily representative of monthly or macroscale distribution trends.
- Abundance to biomass conversion uncertainty: species-specific conversion factors for calcifying plankton are often unavailable. Generalized allometric relationships are used in these cases, introducing additional uncertainty. Furthermore, strong environmental controls on organic and inorganic carbon contents, as well as strain-specific differences, add additional uncertainty.
- Methodological bias has strong impacts on both latitudinal, longitudinal and depth distributions. For instance, for coccolithophores light microscopy tends to underestimate the abundance of lightly calcified species (243-245). These methodological biases not only under-represent the abundance of certain species, but also make “zero” observations generally unquantifiable as a lack of observation could be due to methodological issues.
- Live cell vs dead cell uncertainty: some methods (such as scanning electron microscopy for coccolithophores) do not allow distinction of whether cells were alive or dead at the time of sampling. While this is not an issue for PIC stock estimates, it poses a significant challenge for POC stock estimates. While depth presents a useful cut-off to remove dead cells from POC stocks, for some groups

such as coccolithophores, a depth cut-off might not be appropriate as deep cells could still be alive (e.g. (246)) and should thus be included in POC stocks.

- Active migration presents a challenge for pteropods as estimates will be strongly influenced by the time of day, and will not be representative of the mean biomass over a 24-hour cycle (48).

2. Biocalcification process

Disregarding direct seawater leakage, there are two possible pathways for Ca to reach the site of calcification (SOC): transmembrane transport (TMT) and seawater endocytosis (247). The latter is used by foraminifera, but not by coccolithophores (248-251). Coccolithophores use TMT to transport Ca from seawater into the cell, but depending on the species use vesicles for Ca delivery to the SOC (252-254). The extent to which foraminifera rely on endocytosed seawater as a Ca source is a matter of ongoing debate. It has been suggested that in some species at least, TMT is the major pathway of Ca into the cell (255, 256). In mollusks the mantle delivers the Ca for shell formation, largely via TMT (73, 78, 79, 89, 257).

Besides Ca and inorganic carbon, a biomineral contains organics instrumental in morphogenesis (258-261). The role that the organic material plays might be different in coccolithophores compared to foraminifers and mollusks. In the latter groups shell formation commences with the periodic transport of organics and a precursor phase, amorphous calcium carbonate or vaterite, into the SOC (250, 258, 262-265). In the SOC the precursor packets stabilized by organics transform into the final mineral phase in an organic matrix, resulting in a nanostructure and banding pattern of the shell (266-271) (272). In some coccolithophores precursor phases have been observed, but it is concluded that they deliver Ca continuously without playing a structural role, although a recently discovered minor element stripiness bears superficial similarity to foraminiferal and mollusk banding, an observation that awaits explanation (253, 273-276). In coccolithophores organic material is involved in Ca transport and nucleation, and maybe also in crystal growth (252, 253, 273, 277-280). A cellular structure that is crucial to morphogenesis in all three groups is the cytoskeleton (281-286).

Calcification has evolved independently in mollusks, foraminifers, and coccolithophores, so similarities are convergent and differences to be expected (287).

3. Estimates of CaCO₃ production, export, dissolution, and burial

We used recent estimates of PIC production and shallow export, classifying the estimates based on groups of calcifying plankton (or total) and whether they trace PIC production or shallow export depending on the methodology used (Table S2). We considered estimates based on methodologies which track the biomass of each group and estimates of calcification rate/turnover time as reflecting PIC production. Conversely, we ascribed estimates based on sinking fluxes and/or seawater alkalinity anomalies as tracking export flux. Whether methods utilizing the seasonal cycle of alkalinity in the surface ocean (146, 288) track PIC production or export will depend on the timescale of Alkalinity (Alk) regeneration, and whether this can drive seasonal variability in Alk. As such these were therefore not included in either production or export estimates, as they likely trace something in between. We also excluded the value of Buitenhuis et al. (135) (4.7 Pg) from estimates of total PIC production as it is substantially higher than other estimates, and subsequent work based on a similar biomass dataset revised down the estimates (16). This

revision largely concerned the turnover time of pteropods: a value of 1 day used by Buitenhuis et al. (135) is considered unrealistically low for complex organisms of the size of pteropods with a lifespan of multiple years (Table S1). In the subsequent estimate by Knecht et al. (16) a value of 1 year was used. Such difference in the turnover time has a very large (a factor of 365) influence in the resulting production. Given their size and complexity, the turnover time for pteropods is likely to be substantially higher than 1 day, however, considerable uncertainty remains in pteropod turnover times (Table S1), and turnover time remains a key source of uncertainty in pteropod CaCO₃ production estimates. We note, including the total production estimate of Buitenhuis et al. (135) would increase the discrepancy between estimates of PIC production and export.

For PIC production the total value and proportions were estimated by combining the minimum and maximum of the individual group estimates from the literature. We calculated uncertainties on the group proportions via resampling the min and max values of each group, using a flat probability distribution (Table S3), and report the full range of values (i.e. 1st to 100th percentile) as the uncertainty range on these proportions, without assigning a central value. For foraminifers and pteropods, we used the minimum estimate of export flux as the max value of PIC production, as the former is higher than the latter. There is no mechanistic reason for export to be higher than production, and current estimates of PIC production for foraminifers and pteropods are likely biased on the low side (16).

There are two sources that could contribute to a possible high bias in satellite derived coccolithophore CaCO₃ production estimates. Firstly, in the polar Southern Ocean non-coccolith material (possibly *Phaeocystis* blooms or glacial flour) can contribute to the detected surface 'PIC' signal (139). Given the limited surface area this applies to, this issue is highly unlikely to be a problem at the global integral. Secondly, in the approach of (130), the PIC algorithm does not differentiate between contributions from coccolithophores and coccoliths while the physiological model associates PIC production with coccolithophore growth. As loose coccoliths can remain in the water column for days to weeks (due to their slow sinking speed) the approach of (130) could therefore overestimate calcification rate in regions where coccolith concentration is high but coccolithophore concentration is low (although overall their model estimates agree well with independent water column calcification rate data and do not suggest a bias).

Despite these potential sources of bias, the close agreement between the empirically based ¹⁴C calcification rate satellite algorithm of Balch et al. (129) and the physiological based satellite algorithm of Hopkins et al. (130) despite the very different methodologies and assumptions underpinning them, argues against large biases and adds confidence to the satellite-based approaches. Furthermore, simpler extrapolation methods of in situ ¹⁴C calcification rate data – based on the ratio of coccolithophore calcification to primary production rates, and global primary production estimates (141, 143) or global extrapolation of integrated water column calcification rates (142) – arrive at similar or substantially higher estimates global coccolithophore production (Table S2). Extrapolation of CaCO₃ production rates based on in situ water column biomass data and turnover time estimates also support substantially higher estimates global coccolithophore production (2). Thus, while considerable uncertainty remains in the magnitude of coccolithophore CaCO₃ production, the high production values appear to be a real feature of the data, rather than an artifact of methodological bias.

A rough calculation with the available global water column biomass data and typical traits (Table S1) supports this high coccolithophore production rate. Taking the mean coccolithophore CaCO₃ biomass of 0.88 mg C m⁻³ (289) and a typically PIC:POC ratio of ~1 (Table S1), results in a global coccolithophore CaCO₃ biomass of ~24 Tg C

(integrating globally to a depth of 150m). This is near identical to the satellite-based physiological modelling estimate of Hopkins 2018. Applying a turnover time of 5 days for living coccolithophore biomass gives a global coccolithophore CaCO₃ production rate of ~1740 Tg C yr⁻¹. A turnover time of 3 days (which is more typical for organisms of this size) would result in a CaCO₃ production rate of ~2900 Tg C yr⁻¹.

Estimates of total PIC export flux come from the seawater alkalinity estimates of Sulpis et al. (133), Battaglia et al. (134) and the sediment trap compilation of Neukermans et al. (7). Estimates of export flux from each group came from the sediment trap compilation of Neukermans et al. (7) (38%:42%:20%, coccolithophores: foraminifers: pteropods). Note that while providing a robust constraint on total export, it is not possible to determine group specific fluxes from methods utilizing seawater alkalinity. While many of the sediment trap studies compiled by Neukermans et al. (7) report a substantial proportion of unidentified PIC, even if we assume that all of this is coccolithophore PIC (making coccolithophores 69% of export flux rather than 38%), the resulting coccolith PIC export flux still remains ~50% lower than the minimum estimate of coccolithophore PIC production.

To show the CaCO₃ production, export and burial of each calcifying plankton group (Fig. 4 a), the estimates of total and group-specific CaCO₃ production are from Balch et al. (129), Hopkins et al. (130), Schiebel and Movellan (131), Knecht et al. (16), and Neukermans et al. (7); the total value and proportions are estimated by combining the individual group estimates from across the individual studies (supplemental materials). The uncertainty range on the proportions of CaCO₃ production are 80-98%, <1-15%, and <1-6% for coccolithophores, foraminifers and pteropods, respectively. Estimates of total CaCO₃ export production come from Sulpis et al. (133), Battaglia et al. (134), and Neukermans et al. (7); the estimates of group export production come from the sediment trap compilation of Neukermans et al. (7). Total sediment burial estimates come from Berelson et al. (223), Sulpis et al. (204), and Middleburg et al. (224); the estimates of group burial flux come from Broecker and Clark (137) and there Schiebel et al. (136). Estimates of PIC dissolution in Fig. 4b are from Sulpis et al. (133) and sediment (light grey) CaCO₃ dissolution estimates from Berelson et al. (223), Sulpis et al. (204), and Middleburg et al. (224).

Fig. S1.

Latitude-depth profile of pteropod biomass observations from Knecht et al. (16). Note that while observations extend to 2000 meters, the majority of biomass is found near the surface. Furthermore, observations below 800 meters are mainly a result of postmortem passive sinking or less likely vertical transport from strong downwelling currents (e.g., (220)).

Table S1.

Main traits of the three calcifying plankton groups classified by type and ecological function following the unified topology proposed in Martini et al. (290). Ranges refer to intra-group variability of traits.

Trait type	Trait	Coccolithophores		Planktonic Foraminifers		Shelled Pteropods	
		Characteristic (Variability)	Ref.	Characteristic (Variability)	Ref.	Characteristic (Variability)	Ref.
Morphological	Organism diameter	2-40 μm (High)	(221, 291)	100-1000 μm for adult specimen (High)	(292, 293)	0.1-20 mm (High)	(124)
	Lith/Shell Mineralogy	Calcite (None)	(276, 294)	Calcite (None)	(43)	Aragonite (None)	(124, 295)
	Organic layers within Lith/Shell	Yes (None)	(68, 275, 296)	Yes (None)	(43)	Yes (None)	(161, 297, 298)
	PIC:POC ratio	0-4.8 (High)	(221, 299)	3-6 (Low)	(16)	0.2-0.6 (Low)	(237)
	Level of cellularity	Unicellular (None)	(300)	Unicellular (None)	(43)	Multicellular (None)	(124)
	Food particle size range	<5 μm (Low)	(301)	nm-mm (High)	(302, 303)	μm -mm (High)	(304, 305)
	Defense structures	Coccoliths (None)	(300)	Tests and spines (None)	(43)	Shell (High)	(306)
Life History	Lifespan/longevity	0.1 - 1.5 cell division per day (High)	(299)	Weeks to months, synodic lunar cycle (High)	(43)	1-2 years (High)	(237, 307, 308)
	Resting stages/dormancy	Unknown	-	Possibly	(309)	Unknown	-
	Turnover time (Living Biomass)	0.6-10 days (High)	(130, 142, 299, 310)	Weeks to months (High)	(43)	Several weeks to a year (High)	(2, 16, 237)
Physiological	Photosynthesis ability	Yes (None)	(300, 311)	None or photosymbionts (High)	(312)	No (None)	(313)
	Site of calcification	Intracellular (None)	(66, 68)	Extracellular (None)	(314)	Extracellular (None)	(315)
	Calcification related proton removal	Plasmamembrane H^+ channel (Unknown)	(74, 316)	V-ATPase and a $\text{H}^+/\text{Ca}^{2+}$ exchanger (Unknown)	(82, 85)	Na^+/H^+ exchangers, voltage gated proton channels, and H^+ ATPase (Unknown)	(79, 83, 84)

	Maximum growth rate	1.8 d ⁻¹ (High)	(291, 299)	0.10-3 chamber day ⁻¹ (High)	(317)	0.003-1.1 mm day ⁻¹ (High)	(318-320)
	Starvation tolerance	High (High)	(321)	Unknown	-	Months (High)	(322, 323)
	Feeding rate	Unknown	-	One copepod every 3.3 days on average, for <i>Trilobatus sacculifer</i> . Fed a 1-day-old <i>Artemia</i> sp. nauplius daily (Unknown)	(324, 325)	76-27000 ng pigment ind. ⁻¹ day ⁻¹ (High)	(304)
	Basal respiration	30 to 764 μmol O ₂ [mg Chla] ⁻¹ h ⁻¹ (High)	(326, 327)	0.15 to 6 nmol O ₂ h ⁻¹ per individual (High)	(328, 329)	0.93 to 6 μmol O ₂ [g wet weight] ⁻¹ h ⁻¹ (High)	(54, 55, 330)
Behavioral	Food preference/diet	Unknown	-	Omnivorous (phytoplankton/zooplankton) (High)	(324, 331)	Omnivorous (High)	(304, 332, 333)
	Feeding mode	Phagotrophy (None)	(334-336)	Digestive vacuoles (None)	(324, 331)	Suspension feeders, producing mucous webs from their wings (None)	(121, 123, 305, 337)
	Motility	0-7.5 m d ⁻¹ (High)	(300, 338)	Non-motile (None)	(43)	0.1-9 km d ⁻¹ (High)	(47, 220, 339)
	Individual sinking speed	0.03-2.4 m d ⁻¹ (High)	(14)	80-1500 m d ⁻¹ (High)	(43, 340)	43-1200 m d ⁻¹	(124, 166)
Predation	Predation/Prey	High (High)	(341, 342)	Unknown	(43)	Low (Low)	(20, 304)

Table S2.

Global estimates of CaCO₃ production and export. Mean PIC values (Tg C y⁻¹) (minima-maximum reported in parentheses) and shallow export fluxes of the three calcifying plankton groups.

Reference	Group	Production / Export	Tg C yr ⁻¹ (Range)	Method
(129)	Coccolithophores	Production	1600 (1300-1900)	Satellite based algorithm using empirical relationships with insitu ¹⁴ C calcification rate data
(130)	Coccolithophores	Production	1400 (0 - 3000)	Satellite based algorithm with depth integrated biomass and physiological model for growth rate
(143)	Coccolithophores	Production	2400	Global ¹⁴ C calcification rate dataset. Extrapolation based on mean calcification: primary production rate in dataset (0.05) and global primary production (48.5 Pg C yr ⁻¹)
(141)	Coccolithophores	Production	1000	Global compilation of ¹⁴ C calcification rate. Extrapolation based on calcification: primary production rate in dataset (0.02) by global primary production (50 Pg C yr ⁻¹)
(2)	Coccolithophores	Production	2300-3100	Global extrapolation of North Pacific coccolithophore production rate dataset based on living CaCO ₃ biomass and turnover time estimates
(142)	Coccolithophores	Production	3000	Global extrapolation of Atlantic ¹⁴ C calcification rate dataset
(7)	Coccolithophores	Export	267	Compilation of mesopelagic sediment traps (200-1000m) - mean value integrated over global ocean area
(131)	Foraminifers	Production	25 - 100	Multinets
(16)	Foraminifers	Production	11 (3-27)	MAREDAT extended, calcification rate estimates
(136)	Foraminifers	Export	273 (157-389)	Multinets, empty shells (100m depth export)
(7)	Foraminifers	Export	311	Compilation of mesopelagic sediment traps (200-1000m) - mean value integrated over global ocean area
(16)	Pteropods	Production	14 (9-22)	MAREDAT extended, calcification rate estimates
(7)	Pteropods	Export	100	Compilation of mesopelagic sediment traps (200-1000m) - mean value integrated over global ocean area
(288)	Total	Production/ Export*	1000 (900-1100)	Seasonal surface alkalinity + nutrient cycle
(146)	Total	Production/ Export*	1100 (800-1400)	Seasonal surface alkalinity cycle
(134)	Total	Export	900 (700-1050)	Alkalinity regeneration (TA*)
(133)	Total	Export	912 (770-1050)	Alkalinity regeneration (TA*)
(7)	Total	Export	680	Compilation of mesopelagic sediment traps (200-1000m) - mean value of identified flux estimates, integrated over global ocean area

*Depends on timescale of alkalinity regeneration and whether this can drive seasonal cycles, hence these estimates are not included in the totals for total or export as they likely trace something in between. Brackets indicate uncertainty range, when given.

Table S3.Contributions to total PIC production (Tg C yr⁻¹).

Group	Minimum	Maximum	Percentage (%)
Coccolithophores	1000	3000	90 (74-99)
Foraminifers	11	273*	7 (<1-20)
Pteropods	15	100*	3 (<1-9)
Total	1041	3339	

The minimum and maximum values for each group refer to the minimum and maximum of the mean values reported across the different studies in Table S2, rather than the minimum and maximum within any individual study. The minimum and maximum values for the group percentages and total production is the full uncertainty range (i.e. 1st to 100th percentile) assuming a flat probability distribution between maximum and minimum values of each group.

*Maximum mean value of PIC production taken as minimum of export production estimates when the latter is higher than the former